

The Research on Human Resource Management Problem of Turkish Fast Food Company

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Abstract : Turkey is one of the countries in which fast food service is growing increasingly in the world. The emergence of KFC and McDonald's to Turkish market is affecting every aspects of local fast-food services. The Turkey's famous catering companies named "Simit Sarayi" and "Güllüoğlu" are famous for accepting the Western fast food management service and skills in order to increase their market share. Also, they have created their unique management skills in this field. In this paper, through empirical and comparative study method we will analyze the famous Turkish local fast-food companies and western human resource management. We will argue how to create and adapt the human resource management while the company is economically and socially growing.

Keywords : human resources management, Turkey, fast food, management

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